

The Moderating Role of Close Support Between Online Purchase Intention and Behavior in Senior Adults¹

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Abstract

Although the population is rapidly aging worldwide and in Turkey, and 65+ adults have become an increasingly important market for e-commerce, online purchasing has still not reached the predicted rates. When the antecedents of behavior are examined, intention appears as the most basic predictor, while several factors influence its transformation into behavior. Although the role of facilitator is frequently emphasized in literature, environmental support in the context of assisted shopping can be a factor that limits the experience of technology. This study aims to examine the moderating role of support of relatives in the relationship between online purchase intention and behavior of senior adults. Using stratified sampling, 635 participants were surveyed with the Online Purchase Barriers Scale, Online Purchase Intention Questions, and a three-item Online Purchase Behavior Measure. Relationships were tested via Pearson correlation, and moderation was examined with Hayes' (2013) Process Macro (Model-1). Findings revealed a significant positive relationship between intention and behavior. However, assisted

shopping was negatively correlated with both intention and behavior. Moreover, child/relative support (assisted shopping) moderated the intention-behavior link: when such support was high, the predictive power of intention on behavior increased. This suggests that while support facilitates access, it may also limit older adults' development of independent digital behaviors. In collectivist and traditional societies like Türkiye, family assistance can unintentionally reduce experiential learning by preventing autonomous interaction with technology. The finding that close support regulates the intention-behavior relationship contributes to the national literature and offers insights for other collectivist contexts worldwide.

Keywords: Online Purchase Intention, Online Purchase Behavior, Close Relatives Support, Assisted Shopping.

JEL Codes: D12, D91, J14, L81, Z13

¹This article is derived from a study originally presented at the IX. ASC 2025 Spring Congress (May 15–18, 2025), hosted by İstanbul Gedik University in İstanbul, Türkiye, and has been substantially revised to meet the academic and editorial standards required for publication.

Citation: Tasa, H., Karsu, S., Nurtanış Velioğlu, M., Çoknaz, D., & Özbakır Umut, M. (2025). The Moderating Role of Close Support Between Online Purchase Intention and Behavior in Senior Adults. *Researches on Multidisciplinary Approaches (Romaya Journal)*, 5(SI-IXASC2025): 269-278.

1. Introduction

While the population is rapidly aging worldwide and the elderly market is experiencing an unprecedented process, the elderly population in Türkiye has doubled in the last 60 years, reaching the highest point in the country's history. The 65+ population increased by 29 percent from 6 million 192 thousand 962 people in 2014 to 8 million 722 thousand 806 people in 2023 (TÜİK, 2023). With this increase, the stereotype of "elderly and helpless elderly" is being replaced by the image of "elderly people who actively participate in the process of meeting the needs of themselves and their relatives and who are interested in active life" (Zalega, 2017). In today's digital age of rapid change and transformation, it is important for 65+ senior adults to develop their skills in online processes in order to develop skills that enable active participation in life and to maintain functionality.

Attitudes towards an action affect the behavior itself through the behavioral intention to perform that action (Ajzen, 1991). The transformation of online shopping intention into actual behavior depends on various individual and environmental factors that affect intention and behavior. Several factors in the online purchase decision process can facilitate or inhibit the online purchasing behavior of 65+ senior adults. In fact, although they have become an increasingly important potential market for e-commerce (Lian & Yen, 2014) and are economically disadvantaged, older consumers are not sufficiently involved in online shopping processes that are known to offer low price advantages (International Trade Administration, 2024; Wilson, 2021). Understanding these factors is critical to creating effective strategies for e-commerce, especially as the shift to online retail continues to gain momentum.

For 65+ senior consumers, health (Gerontechnology, 2024), risk avoidance (Zhang, 2023), traditional structures (Elimelech et al., 2024), socio-economic differences/constraints (Help Age International, 2024; Çınar & Altunay, 2024) are factors that inhibit online purchasing behavior, while functional characteristics such as ease, convenience, time saving (Larano et al, 2023), psychological characteristics such as hedonic motivation (Deral & Kazançoğlu, 2021) and work-based use (Karsu et al., 2019) are among the driving factors. In addition to these, the social environment of senior adults (close others like members of the community they live in, their families, etc.) also plays an important role in influencing their technology use, and thus their attitudes and behaviors towards online shopping. Close other can be define as "a family member, friend, neighbour or paid assistant who helps an older adult with various daily living activities" (Latulipe et al., 2022) and adapting to and using new technologies is among these activities

today. When senior adults can see and try the technologies used by other individuals in the social environments they interact with, it becomes easier for them to adopt the relevant technology (Luijckx et al. 2015), and supportive relationships positively affect senior adults' use of different technologies (Chen & Chan, 2014). Similarly, there is research suggesting that senior adults can enhance their mobile purchasing experiences through social interactions such as learning, collaboration and assistance (Seo, et al., 2023).

However, research also shows that in some cases, the social environment may play an inhibiting role rather than an encouraging role in the use of new technologies (Umut Özbakır et al., 2022; Karsu et al., 2019). Although they have a positive attitude towards online shopping, they may be hindered by family members (Ismail & Abdul Wahid, 2022), increased family support may reduce the satisfaction of psychological needs in some cases (Zhao et. al., 2021), and overprotective attitudes of younger family members may push senior adults away from online purchasing behavior (Deng et. al., 2025). Based on these studies in the literature, this study investigates whether the online purchasing experiences of 65+ senior adults are negatively affected by this helping behavior in Türkiye, where the care obligation of the elderly parent belongs to children and relatives and care needs are expected to be met within the family (Selçuk & Avcı, 2016; Tamkoç et al., 2023).

Although behavioral intention is an important predictor in the emergence of behavior, the presence of certain inhibiting factors may prevent the transformation of intention into behavior. In collectivist structures, the support and assistance of family elders/senior adults, which are seen as beneficial, may hinder the potential of senior adults to try new behaviors and/or improve themselves because they do not feel obliged. From this point of view, the aim of the study is to examine whether the support of children and relatives is an inhibiting factor in the presence of intention, which is an important antecedent of online purchasing behavior of 65+ individuals. In addition to testing the moderating role of the support of family members and other relatives in the relationship between online purchase intention and behavior, the study focuses on the inhibiting role of this support, which is seen as a facilitating factor in the literature. This different perspective is very important in terms of creating a new understanding of the facilitating and inhibiting factors of online purchasing behavior both in Türkiye and in collectivist structures such as Türkiye. The results of the research are expected to contribute to the practices to be developed for online purchasing, new research on the decision-making process, and social policies to be developed for senior adults.

2. Conceptual Framework and Hypothesis Development

Behavior can be defined as any action or function that an organism performs in response to external or internal stimuli that can be objectively observed or measured and intention is a conscious decision made in advance to perform that behavior (American Psychological Association [APA], n.d.). These theories have also been used to provide explanations for attitudes towards e-commerce, defined as the process of buying and selling products and services through online tools (Vărzaru et al., 2021), and the use of new technologies.

The relationship between purchase intention and actual purchase behavior plays a crucial role in consumer decision-making. Research shows that an individual's purchase intention is a strong determinant of subsequent behavior. This research emphasizing the relationship between intention and behavior is mostly based on the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) (Fishbein & Ajzen, 1975), Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) (Ajzen, 1991), Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) (Davis, 1987) and Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) (Venkatesh et al., 2003).

TRA which is one of the important theories of social psychology suggests that individuals evaluate behavioral outcomes and decide whether or not to perform the behavior and immediate determinant of behavior is individual's behavioral intentions (Fishbein & Ajzen, 1975). The determinants of a person's intention are their positive or negative assessment of the behavior (attitude) and how they perceive social pressures to perform or not perform to that behavior (subjective norm) (Ajzen, 1991). Attitude is determined by behavioral beliefs (beliefs about the likelihood of various consequences) and evaluations of how good or bad it would be if those consequences happened. Subjective norm is determined by beliefs about what specific important others think one should do and how much one is motivated to comply with those important others (Trafimow, 2009). In TPB (Ajzen, 1991), which is an extended model of TRA, the determinants of a behavior are Attitudes, Subjective Norms and also Perceived Behavioral Control. According to this theory, the direct antecedent of behavior is the intention to perform the relevant behavior, and as the control over one's behavior increases, the likelihood of the intention turning into behavior increases (Ajzen, 2020). If there is a positive attitude that includes the knowledge that the environment is supportive and that there is no barrier to behavior, the person's intention and behavior will be positively affected (Han et al., 2018). TAM (Davis, 1987) is a model frequently used to provide a theoretical basis for the attitudes, intentions and behaviors of older individuals towards online purchasing. The theory, which is an adaptation of the

TRA for the use of information technologies (Dishaw & Strong, 1999), was later extended by Venkatesh and Bala (2008) as TAM3, which provides a "comprehensive nomological network" covering the determinants of the adoption and use of information technologies at the individual level (Davis & Granić, 2024). In the theory, behavioral intention is presented as an antecedent of technology use; perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use and their antecedents are included as antecedents of intention (Venkatesh & Bala, 2008).

According to the UTAUT model, which is an integration of TPB, TAM and TRA models and reflects the impact of users' intentions to use new information technologies quite well, performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence, facilitating conditions, gender, age, together with the moderating effect of experience, largely explain the intention and behavior to use technology (Venkatesh et al., 2003). In 2012, in order to examine the acceptance and use of technology in the consumer context, UTAUT was extended to include hedonic motivation, defined as the enjoyment or pleasure derived from the use of a technology; price value, defined as the cognitive trade-off between consumers' perceived benefits of applications and the monetary cost of using them; and habituation, defined as a perceptual construct reflecting the results of previous experiences (Venkatesh et al., 2012).

It is seen that the most important antecedent of behavior in all the models mentioned is intention. Many studies have been conducted to measure online purchase intention (e.g., Lim, et al., 2016; Yılmaz, 2016) and behavior (e.g., Çelik & Taş, 2021) directly and indirectly through attitudes (e.g., Akroush & Al-Debei, 2015; Chetioui et al., 2021). In these studies, it has been found that online purchase intention and positive attitudes towards online purchasing positively predict online purchasing behavior. Based on these findings, the first hypothesis of the study is given below.

H1: Online purchase intention positively predicts online purchase behavior.

In understanding online shopping behavior, it is important to consider inhibitory and driver factors because they play an important role in shaping consumers' behavior (Ha et al., 2019). Events that change social practices, such as the pandemic, have also led elderly individuals to change and adapt their shopping methods. Restrictions such as curfews have become one of the factors driving the increase in online shopping (Fuentes et al., 2022). In other words, the limitations imposed by the pandemic can be considered a factor that increased the intention to online shopping and, indirectly, the behavior itself. However, during this process, the support of relatives may lead to the partial or complete assumption of this responsibility by another person rather than

the development of autonomous behavior. In assisted shopping, which is defined as shopping involving close friends and relatives, product orders are delegated to others acting as mediators (Hansson et al., 2022). In this case, close support may become an inhibitor of autonomous online shopping behavior rather than support for using an online platform.

The literature shows that consumers' behavioral intentions lead to actual use of online shopping platforms (Ching et al., 2021). In all of the aforementioned models, in addition to intention as antecedents of behavior, many driving and inhibiting factors are included together. However, in some contextual conditions, factors that are expressed as driving forces (such as the number of household members) may also appear as inhibiting factors. One of the important reasons for this is social norms. Social norms affect behavior and thus consumer behavior (Melnyk, et. al., 2021). In structures such as Türkiye, where the responsibility of caring for elderly parents belongs to children and relatives, the caregiving obligation sometimes even restricts the caregivers' own lives (Doğanay & Güven, 2019). Since the needs of the elderly are met by their relatives, they do not have to be active, including their daily chores. While this may seem unchangeable and uncomfortable for seniors, a study conducted in Türkiye found that older adults who have children receive more and more help from their children as they get older, and that this help contributes positively to their overall well-being (Inel et al., 2021). There is also a tendency

towards extended family models where it is generally accepted to live with their children as next-door neighbors (Imamoğlu, 2015), which does not allow the senior adult to be independent/autonomous. This situation is an example of how the presence of relatives prevents the active participation of 65+ individuals in life. However, in the UTAUT model, the facilitating effects of the environment are included. The other hypotheses of the study, which are based on the social norms in Türkiye and the sense of commitment of people who undertake the task of caring for senior adults, are given below.

H2: Assisted shopping negatively predicts online purchase behavior.

H3: Assisted shopping has a moderating role between online purchase intention and behavior.

3. Method

3.1. Research Model

In this study, correlational survey method, one of the quantitative research methods, was used. Correlational research designs allow for the examination of natural associations between variables without establishing causal relationships (Creswell and Creswell, 2017). This method is important because it allows data to be collected from a large group of participants in a short period of time and at a lower cost (Büyüköztürk et al., 2017). The model tested in the research is given below.

Figure 1. Research Model

3.2. Population and Sample

The population of the study consists of 65+ senior adults living in Türkiye. Data collection processes within the scope of the study were carried out following the ethical approval of Bolu Abant İzzet Baysal University Human Research Ethics Committee in Social Sciences with the decision number 2019/08

dated 10.08.2019. Stratified sampling method was used to reach 635 participants (262 women, 373 men) aged 65+ from 14 provinces of Türkiye (two provinces were randomly selected from each of the seven regions). The selected provinces, the elderly population in these provinces, and the number of data collected from each province are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Distribution of the Sample by Region and Province

Regions	Randomly Selected Provinces	65+ Population	Number of Surveys Reached
Mediterranean	Adana	167 347	69
	Antalya	186 805	77
Central Anatolia	Karaman	28 591	14
	Eskişehir	93 452	40

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Blacksea	Zonguldak	68 339	28
	Kastamonu	62 719	26
Southeastern Anatolia	Gaziantep	104 087	43
	Mardin	42 687	22
Marmara	Edirne	55 094	23
	Kocaeli	128 625	53
Eastern Anatolia	Erzurum	62 382	26
	Kars	22 267	11
Aegean	İzmir	450 925	186
	Uşak	41 437	17
TOTAL		1.514.757	635

When the distribution of the participants according to their educational status was examined, it was seen that 17.6% had primary school (N=101), 11.5% had secondary school (N=66), 31.2% had high school (N=179), 9.1% had associate's degree (N=52), 26.1% had bachelor's degree (N=150) and 4.5%

had postgraduate degree (N=26). While 95.1% of the participants have children (N=604), 4.6% do not have children (N=29). 31.3% of the participants stated that they shop online themselves (N=199) and 52.4% of them shop online through their relatives (N=333).

Table 2. Sample Demographic Information

Variable	Category	% - N (635)
Age	65-74	82.8 – 526
	75-84	16.1 – 102
	85+	1.1 – 7
Sex	Female	41.3 – 262
	Male	58.7 – 373
Education	Primary School	17.6 – 101
	Secondary School	11.5 – 66
	High School	31.2 – 179
	Associate Degree	9.1 – 52
	Undergraduate	26.1 – 150
	Graduate	4.5 – 26
Having a child	Yes	95.4 – 604
	No	4.6 – 29
Buying online in person	Yes	31.4 – 199
	No	68.6 – 435
Buying online through relatives	Yes	52.4 – 333
	No	47.6 – 302

3.3. Data Collection Tools

Within the scope of the study, data were collected from the participants by face-to-face survey method. Demographic information forms were used to collect data from participants on their age, gender, educational status, province of residence, whether they had children, and whether they shopped online

themselves or through their relatives. 4-item 5-point Likert (1-Totally Disagree; 5-Totally Agree) Online Purchase Intention Scale (Çelik, 2009) used for participants' intentions to purchase online (sample item, I will purchase online as soon as possible). Chan's (2001) behavioral measurements consisting of three questions (1- How often do you shop on the Inter-

net?, 2- How much do you spend on your online purchases?, 3-How much do you buy products on the Internet?) were used for online purchasing behavior. The items were translated into Turkish by researchers and checked for clarity. In a preliminary study conducted with a sample of 415 participants, it was found that three items explained 73.77% of the variance, with item factor loadings ranging from .718 to .933. The Cronbach alpha reliability coefficient was calculated as .794. Child/relative support was measured through the Assisted Shopping subscale (sample item, "Since children meet all their needs, there is no need to shop online") of the Online Purchase Barriers Scale (Nurtaniş Velioğlu et al., 2022). This subscale is a subdimension of the online shop-

ping barriers scale and includes attitudes that older individuals do not need to shop because their relatives carry out the online shopping process for themselves. Within the scope of the study, the internal consistency coefficients for the measurement tools were found to be .937 for Online Purchase Intention, .898 for Online Purchasing Behavior, and .845 for Child/Relative support.

4. Findings

Within the scope of the study, normality assumptions were tested for the variables and it was seen that kurtosis skewness values were within ±1 (Table 3) and Z scores were within ±3.29.

Table 3. Descriptive Statistics of Variables

	\bar{X}	sd	Kur.	Skew.	Cron. α
Assisted shopping	3.08	1.10	-.032	-.888	.845
Online purchase intention	2.82	1.12	-.057	-.876	.937
Online purchase behavior	1.93	.92	.547	-.782	.898

First of all, Pearson Correlation analysis was conducted to examine the relationships between the variables. According to the results of the analysis, there was a significant positive relationship between online purchase intention and behavior ($r = .631$,

$p < .01$). Assisted shopping was found to be negatively correlated with both online purchase intention ($r = -.298$, $p < .01$) and online purchase behavior ($r = -.259$, $p < .01$).

Tablo 4. Pearson Correlation Analysis Findings for the Relationships between Variables

	\bar{X}	sd	1	2	3
1. Assisted shopping	3.08	1.10	–		
2. Online purchase intention	2.82	1.12	-.298**	–	
3. Online purchase behavior	1.93	0.92	-.259**	.631**	–

** $p < .01$

The moderating role of assisted shopping in the relationship between online purchase intention and behavior was tested with the Process Macro extension (Model-1) developed by Hayes (2013). The results of the analysis showed that the model obtained for the moderating effect was significant ($R^2 = .414$; $F(3-631) = 148.28$; $p < .01$) and that assisted shopping had a moderating role in the relationship between intention and behavior ($\beta = -0.070$; $p < .01$). The prediction of online purchase intention on behavior is more significant when assisted shopping is high ($\beta = .412$; $p < .01$) than when it is medium ($\beta = .482$; $p < .01$) and low ($\beta = .569$; $p < .01$). Conditional effect analysis revealed that the effect of intention on behavior remained statistically significant all observed values of assisted shopping. Specifically, at low levels of assisted

shopping, the effect of intention on behavior was stronger ($\beta = .569$, $SE = .03$, $t = 16.83$, $p < .001$, 95% CI [.50, .64]). At average levels of assisted shopping, the effect remained significant but weaker ($\beta = .482$, $SE = .03$, $t = 17.87$, $p < .001$, 95% CI [.43, .53]). At high levels of assisted shopping, the effect of intention on behavior was further reduced yet still significant ($\beta = .412$, $SE = .04$, $t = 10.82$, $p < .001$, 95% CI [.34, .49]). Johnson–Neyman analysis indicated that there were no transition points within the observed range of the moderator, suggesting that the effect of intention on behavior was consistently significant across all levels of assisted shopping. Figure 2 and Table 5 provide detailed information on the interaction effect of online purchase intention and assisted shopping.

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Table 5. The Moderating Role of Assisted Shopping on the Relationship between Online Purchase Intention and Behavior

Variables	β	SE	t	p	%95 CI	
					LLCI.	ULCI.
Constant	.116	.230	.504	.614	-.336	.568
Online purchase intention	.708	.070	10.150	.000	.571	.845
Assisted shopping	.131	.067	1.955	.051	-.001	.262
Online purchase int. X Ass. shop.	-.070	.022	-3.205	.001	-.112	-.027
Model Summary	R	R2	F	p	Δ R2	Δ F
	.643	.414	148.281	.000	.010	10.273

Dependent variable: Online purchase behavior

Note: The figure shows the interaction of online purchase intention and assisted shopping (close support). The blue line represents the low close support (16th percentile); the purple line represents the average close support (50th percentile); and the red line represents the high close support (84th percentile).

Figure 2. The Interaction of Assisted Shopping and Online Purchase Intention

5. Discussion

Increased familiarity with digital technology, coupled with the constraints of social isolation resulting from events such as the COVID-19 pandemic, has also had various impacts on the purchasing processes of the elderly. In Türkiye, there are limited studies on the facilitating and inhibiting factors affecting online purchasing decisions in the elderly consumer market, where internet use is rapidly expanding. Since the difference in cultural structure will cause some differences in decision-making processes, studies focusing on the social structure of Türkiye are very important.

Although it is a positive situation that the elderly are supported by their wide and/or narrow social circles, relatives, etc., and that their work is seen by their relatives on their behalf, it is among the inhibitors of online shopping on the basis of this study. Şah and Eroğlu (2022) state that individuals cannot be considered separately from the society they live in, and that the cultural environment affects individuals' value judgments, norms, behavior patterns, roles, language use, and thus their ways of thinking. Naturally,

the elderly, like all members of society, cannot be considered separately from the cultural environment in which they live. In Türkiye, there is a functional and psychological tendency to live in extended families and care for the elderly is seen as an obligation of close family and kinship relations (Imamoğlu & Imamoğlu, 1996). In traditional family structures, children are more interested in their parents and often buy things that parents need on their behalf (Wang & Jiang, 2021). According to Pantano et al. (2022), older consumers see family members as the first point of contact for help with technology, rely on their families, and as a result, the autonomy of individual shopping is severely limited. The fact that extended family relations are intense in Türkiye is thought to support the sharing of daily responsibilities and the automatic removal of individual workloads from them as well as affecting the social relations of the elderly. These results are consistent with the findings that cultural differences have an impact on online purchasing behaviors (Smith, et. al, 2013) and that social influence has less online purchasing impact in Türkiye compared to other cultures (Gurcan, 2017).

When family support decreases, the impulse to buy online may intensify, suggesting a compensatory mechanism that suggests that these individuals may rely more on their individual decision-making processes in the absence of external incentives. Indeed, perceived behavioral control in the Theory of Planned Behavior (Ajzen, 1991) is related to having more control over one's behavior. Therefore, contrary to popular belief, external support may become an inhibitor of online purchasing behavior by interfering with the control over behavior and the hedonic pleasure emphasized in the UTAUT model (Venkatesh et al., 2003).

This study has shown that child/relative support may be an inhibiting factor in the relationship between online purchase intentions and behaviors of 65+ senior adults. In this respect, it differs from other studies in the literature that suggest that support may be a facilitating factor. This differentiation may be explained by the fact that in collectivist structures, the duty of caring for the elderly is imposed on family members. In collectivist structures such as Türkiye's social dynamics, it can be said that some behaviors that are seen as for the benefit of family elders/senior adults limit their adaptation in terms of experiencing new innovations, new technologies, new consumption processes, and limit their potential to try new behaviors and improve themselves because they do not feel obliged. Increased support may facilitate a smoother transition to online shopping, while decreased support may paradoxically push older adults to be more decisive in their purchase intentions. Support from relatives can sometimes be "doing on behalf of" rather than "leading," which can unintentionally limit older people's exposure to online purchasing. This ambivalence underlines the complexity of online shopping behaviors among older adults and calls for further research to examine these relationships in depth.

Self-determination theory, which focuses on the effects of social environment on attitudes, values, behaviors and motivation, argues that being development-oriented and having a motivation for self-improvement are inherent characteristics of human nature (Deci & Ryan, 2012). Although the theory suggests that individuals can fulfill this basic need if the environment supports autonomy, there are studies showing that relatedness is a more important need than autonomy in Eastern cultures (Markus et al., 1996). When it comes to 65+ senior adults adapting to change, their intrinsic motivation to experience autonomy and success may be replaced by a desire to share this process with others with whom they are related. This relatedness therefore has the potential to be a barrier to autonomy and development. When support undermines a sense of autonomy, it can prevent online purchase intentions from turning into behavior.

From a practical perspective, these findings suggest that interventions should target not only older adults but also their family members. Awareness programs can help family members transition from a caregiver role to a supporter role, thereby promoting autonomy rather than dependence. E-commerce platforms can support this process by designing age-appropriate user interfaces and offering interactive training courses that encourage independent use. Similarly, community-based digital literacy initiatives can give older adults the confidence and skills they need to shop online without relying excessively on family members. By reducing the unintended inhibiting effects of close support, these measures can increase older adults' participation in the digital marketplace and promote broader acceptance of technologies.

This study is considered to be an important contribution to the literature in Türkiye in terms of addressing close support as one of the inhibitors of online purchasing behaviors and addressing the complex relationship between support and behavior. Future studies can offer a more in-depth perspective on the purchasing decisions of 65+ individuals by examining the cognitive characteristics, household size and support received from their close environment together. In addition, it is very important to seek an answer to the question of whether senior adults receive support because they do not trust in the process of adapting to new technologies or whether they do not trust because they receive support and cannot be autonomous. In this study, the majority of participants were between the ages of 65 and 74, while the number of participants aged 75 and older was limited. This situation limits the generalizability of the findings, particularly to the older age group (75+). In future research, working with samples that more evenly represent older adults will increase the validity of findings related to online purchasing behavior across a wider age range.

Acknowledgements

This study was supported by TUBITAK within the scope of SOBAG 1001 project number 119K945. We would like to thank TUBITAK for their support in the realization of this study.

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